

Real-Time Quadrotor Flight Controller on STM32: Design and Implementation of Error-State Kalman Filter and Quaternion Control

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Abstract—This document presents the design and implementation of a quadrotor unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) flight controller (FC), developed from scratch using the STM32F405 microcontroller unit (MCU). To achieve reliable flight stabilization and state estimation in a resource-constrained environment, the system includes the implementation of an Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF), which fuses IMU, magnetometer, barometer, and GNSS signals to estimate the precise state. A quaternion-based attitude control is used to avoid singularities during maneuvers. Additionally, position and velocity Proportional control is integrated as a cascaded architecture. To satisfy real-time requirements, a real-time operating system (RTOS) is used. FreeRTOS manages task scheduling guaranteeing a 1kHz control loop, while the Dshot600 protocol is used for accurate motor speed control. Furthermore, the adopted modular software architecture facilitates further system upgrades and maintenance. The results demonstrate that the advanced estimation and control algorithm can be executed on low-power, resource-constrained embedded hardware, enabling low-cost but high-performance flight control solutions for small quadrotor UAV systems.

Index Terms—STM32, ESKF, RTOS, Sensor Fusion, Quaternion Control, PID control

I. INTRODUCTION

Building a quadrotor UAV has become accessible with the use of commercial flight controllers and open-source systems. While these commercial solutions offer powerful performance and an intuitive user experience, they obscure the internal logic behind the high abstraction layers and large-scale code. Consequently, this complexity prevents engineering students or novice researchers from developing a deep understanding of how the low-level system actually operates.

To gain this deeper understanding, this project adopts a hybrid way of designing the whole system. The firmware follows a hybrid bare-metal/RTOS architecture: hardware control is fully bare-metal via direct register manipulation, while FreeRTOS is used for high-level task scheduling. The system's sensor drivers, Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF) algorithm, control algorithm, motor mixer, and data parsers are built entirely from scratch without relying on the STM32 HAL library or any commercial flight controllers.

This represents a shift of perspective from a passive user to an active designer. Implementing a hardware register level

manipulation in the system was not driven solely by the pursuit of higher performance, but also by the educational value gained by the exposure of the lower layer of the FC: sensor timing, internal architecture of a MCU, hardware communication, bus interfaces, etc.

Ultimately, while using a commercial FC might be more efficient and powerful, this project's goal was never about outperforming any commercial FCs, but providing a case where the inner mechanisms of a quadrotor UAV FC can be studied and modified with ease.

The remainder of this report is organized as follows. System hardware architecture is introduced in Section II. Section III describes the firmware architecture and its implementation, which focuses on the hybrid bare-metal/RTOS architecture. While this section describes how the algorithms are scheduled and integrated into the MCU, their mathematical formulations are discussed separately. Section IV and Section V focuses on the mathematical structure and derivation of the state estimation, sensor fusion, sensor calibration method, and control algorithm. Section VI demonstrates the experimental results, including filter tuning, flight control response, and timing analysis. Section VII concludes the report with a brief summary.

II. SYSTEM HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

This section contains the overall hardware architecture design of the quadrotor system. It presents the selection and integration of key electronic components. Furthermore, the frame structure and the mechanical integration are to be discussed.

A. Overview of Hardware Architecture

The quadrotor UAV platform is built on a standard 330mm wheelbase frame adopting an X-configuration. This symmetrical shape significantly simplifies the modeling and implementation of the motor mixing algorithm.

To facilitate direct modifications and debugging, the FC is implemented as a hand-wired prototype on a perfboard. This allows immediate probing of sensor signals, which is essential for early stage prototyping.

Fig. 1. Hardware block diagram of the proposed quadrotor UAV system.

Fig. 1 illustrates the overall hardware architecture and data flow. At the core, the system is designed around the STM32F405 MCU, which manages the state estimation, control loops, and sensor data acquisition. The architecture seen in a broad perspective, has three noteworthy points.

First, the communication buses are used differently for each component based on their characteristics. These characteristics are detailed in Section II-C.

Second, a two-stage power regulation method is implemented. As depicted, the 11.1V battery voltage is first stepped down to 5V, via a battery eliminator circuit (BEC) for the GNSS module, which has a 5V input. Then this 5V is stepped down to 3.3V via a low dropout regulator (LDO), providing voltage for the MCU and other sensors. This two-stage power regulation not only enables power for the GNSS, but also ensures that the switching ripple noise from the BEC does not affect the noise sensitive sensors which have a voltage supply rail of 3.3V.

Lastly, to ensure convenient debugging and firmware flashing, the architecture includes a development interface that groups the serial wire debug (SWD) port and the UART1 serial console. This interface is designed to be detachable, allowing for debugging during development and reducing weight while flight is operational.

Detailed specifications and selected components are listed in Table I.

B. MCU

The STM32F405RGT6 was selected as the main processor primarily because of its computational abilities. It features a single-precision floating-point unit (FPU) which is critical for executing complex matrix operations that are used by the ESKF algorithm in real-time. Furthermore, the direct memory access (DMA) allows for handling high-speed sensor data

TABLE I
HARDWARE COMPONENT SPECIFICATIONS.

Category	Component	Model	Remarks
Processing	MCU	STM32F405RGT6	Cortex-M4, FPU (8MHz HSE)
Sensing	6-axis IMU	ICM-42688-P	SPI Interface, Low-noise
	Magnetometer	BMM150	External compass
	Barometer	MS5611-01BA03	24-bit ADC
	GNSS	Matek M10Q-5883	Ublox M10, 5V Input
Comm	RF Module	NRF24L01+	2.4GHz Transceiver
Power	Battery	LiPo 3S	11.1V, 2200mAh
	BEC	Matek Micro BEC	5V output
	LDO	ME6231A33PG	3.3V output
Actuation	Motor	Sunnysky x2212	980KV BLDC
	ESC	Reaper F4	Supports DShot600
	Propeller	Self Lock Prop	8x4.5in
Structure	Frame	F330	X-Configuration

acquisition and motor signal generation possible with minimal CPU intervention. This architecture not only reduces process overhead, but also ensures the deterministic timing of the control loop at the same time.

In addition, the MCU is specified to operate on a core frequency of 168MHz. But to fully operate at a frequency of 168MHz, the adaptive real-time (ART) accelerator needs to be properly enabled. Enabling allows for an equivalent performance to a 0-wait state program execution from flash memory at a frequency up to 168MHz.

Coupled with a 192KB SRAM, this architecture provides a sufficient processing headroom for the 1kHz main control loop despite the heavy computational load and strict timing constraints.

C. Sensors

1) *Inertial Measurement Unit*: The ICM-42688-P, a high-precision 6-axis MEMS motion tracking device, is selected as the main inertial measurement unit (IMU). Providing acceleration and angular velocity data, it serves as the primary input source of the ESKF algorithm on its prediction step.

TABLE II
IMU COMPARISON WITH LEGACY MODELS.

Specification	ICM-42688-P	ICM-20948	MPU-6000
Gyro noise ($\text{dps}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$)	0.0028	0.015	0.005
Accel noise ($\mu\text{g}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$)	0.0028	0.015	0.005
Max output data rate: gyro/accel (kHz)	32 / 32	9 / 4.5	8 / 1
SPI max frequency (MHz)	24	7	1
Embedded filters	Notch, AAF, LPF	LPF, Averaging filter	LPF

Table II compares the specification of ICM-42688-P and two other legacy sensors that were widely adopted in multirotor UAV systems or robotics. ICM-42688-P provides superior performance with lower noise and a higher output data rate. The 21MHz high-speed SPI interface implemented in this system ensures minimum data latency. Additionally, the embedded anti-alias filter (AAF) and its low-pass filter (LPF) are utilized to process the raw data prior to transfer to the MCU.

Although higher performance IMUs exist, the ICM-42688-P was selected as the optimal choice for the system, considering the trade-offs between cost, noise density, interface clock frequency, and market availability.

2) *Magnetometer*: The BMM150, a 3-axis geomagnetic sensor, is utilized for the correction of the quadrotor UAV's heading. It offers a high magnetic field resolution of $0.3\mu\text{T}$ making it suitable for accurate measurements. Despite its accuracy, this type of sensor is highly susceptible to electromagnetic interference (EMI) generated by high current components such as ESCs and motors, as well as wiring, and nearby metal structures like steel screws or supports. Each of these factors interfere with the appropriate measuring of the Earth's true magnetic field. A magnetometer can't directly measure the Earth's true magnetic field, as it measures the local magnetic field which is a distorted form from the Earth's true magnetic field due to nearby elements. An ellipsoid fitting method is used to extract the magnetometer calibration parameters. These are utilized to calibrate the magnetometer to correct the offset and scale distortions, which will be detailed in Section IV.

However, while the ellipsoid fitting method effectively compensates for static distortions, it cannot correct dynamic interference due to changing currents. Therefore, physical isolation of the magnetometer from the high current components is recommended for reliable measurement results.

For the hardware communication interface, the sensor supports SPI interface and the I2C interface to be utilized. Given that magnetometers typically have low output data rates (ODR), the I2C interface was selected. Furthermore, using I2C, the number of required pins can be significantly reduced compared to SPI, thereby keeping the overall design simple.

3) *Barometer*: The MS5611-01BA03, a barometric pressure sensor, is selected for the pressure-derived altitude estimation of the quadrotor UAV. It provides a high resolution 24-bit ADC, which allows for detecting small altitude changes as small as 10cm. As the MEMS pressure component is temperature sensitive, to achieve accurate altitude measurement, an embedded temperature sensor is used for temperature compensation.

However, aerodynamic disturbances caused by propeller wash or pressure generated during high-speed flight, create a significant amount of noise in altitude measurements. To mitigate this, a small open-cell foam was installed around the barometer, which is detailed in Section II-G.

For the hardware communication interface, the I2C interface was selected. This decision is driven by the same logical rationale described in Section II-C2, considering the design simplification and the sensor's ODR.

4) *GNSS Module*: The Matek M10Q-5883 GNSS module is utilized for the measurement of global positioning and velocity. Powered by the u-blox M10 platform, it supports concurrent reception of multiple GNSS constellations (GPS, GLONASS, GALILEO, BDS). This multi-constellation capability significantly improves the positional accuracy compared to single-constellation GNSS modules.

To ensure optimal signal reception, the antenna is required to face the sky without any interference. Therefore, the module is mounted on a mast on top of the frame, physically clearing any objects or structures that block the signal.

Although an embedded magnetometer QMC5883L is installed in the module itself, it is not used for this project. While the QMC5883L advertises a higher theoretical resolution ($0.2\mu\text{T}$) compared to the BMM150 ($0.3\mu\text{T}$), its datasheet lacks detailed specification such as RMS noise characteristics, which are essential for overall performance. Due to its lack of explicit performance specification, the BMM150 which is detailed in Section II-C2 is selected as the magnetometer for this project.

For the hardware communication interface, the UART interface is used. The binary-based UBX protocol is utilized for its higher data transmission rate and stronger data reliability from its 2-byte checksum verification, compared to the NMEA protocol.

D. RF Communication

Wireless RF communication between the ground transmitter and the quadrotor UAV is established using the Nordic Semiconductor nRF24L01+ 2.4GHz transceiver module. It uses the SPI interface for hardware communication, ensuring minimal latency for control.

The Enhanced ShockBurst (ESB) protocol is utilized for data packet transmission. It offers automatic acknowledgments, cyclic redundancy check (CRC) at a hardware level, which are essential for robust communication for real-time quadrotor UAV systems.

E. Actuation

The actuation system is designed to provide sufficient thrust and stable control for the quadrotor UAV. It contains three main components: brushless DC (BLDC) motors, electronic speed controllers (ESC), and propellers.

1) *Motor and Propeller*: A Sunnysky X2212 980KV BLDC motor and 8045 propeller is utilized together for sufficient thrust in the actuation system. The combination of an 8-inch propeller and low-KV motor which is an optimal selection for a 330mm wheelbase frame, provides a thrust-to-weight ratio of approximately 2:1, ensuring sufficient maneuverability and flight capability.

2) *ESC*: To drive 4 motors, Foxeer Reaper F4 45A 4in1 ESC was selected. The main decision criteria was whether the ESC hardware supports the DShot digital protocol. DShot protocol replaces the traditional analog PWM interface with a digital based and CRC protected protocol. This eliminates the need for any throttle range calibration, reduces noise

susceptibility, and ensures higher precision in motor speed control.

F. Power

The power distribution system is designed to provide stable voltage levels to all system components. The primary source of the power system is a 3-cell (3S) lithium polymer (LiPo) battery with a capacity of 2200mAh and a nominal voltage of 11.1V. Its nominal voltage and capacity were selected considering the optimal balance between total weight and estimated flight time.

As first described in Section II-A, a two-stage power regulation method is implemented for the operation of components with different voltage supply requirements, and to protect noise sensitive components. The 11.1V battery is first stepped down to 5V using a switching battery eliminator circuit (BEC), then further stepped down to 3.3V using a low dropout (LDO) linear regulator.

By using the BEC, high input voltages are converted into low output voltages with minimal heat generation, ensuring high conversion efficiency. Also, the 5V rail directly powers the GNSS module which requires a 5V input. While ensuring high conversion efficiency, a switching BEC has a problem on which it generates a voltage ripple noise that can be harmful for noise-sensitive sensors. To mitigate this, an LDO is utilized for stepping down to 3.3V. By the LDO's high power supply rejection ratio (PSRR), it filters out the ripple noise passed down from the BEC, providing a stable and low-noise 3.3V supply rail for the MCU and its connected sensors.

Regarding the noise-sensitive characteristic of a GNSS chip, signal integrity is ensured by two complementary mechanisms. Matek M10Q-5883's onboard low-noise 3.3V regulator and the physical separation by mounting the module on a mast (as described in Section II-C4), significantly reduces noise interference.

G. Mechanical Integration

The mechanical integration of the quadrotor UAV focuses on three main integration strategies throughout the system: Vibration dampening, barometer shielding, and strategic wiring.

1) *Vibration Dampening*: Motor actuation generates high-frequency mechanical vibrations that increase the IMU's noise level, ultimately leading the degradation of ESKF state estimation and flight stability. Rubber vibration dampers (O-rings in this case) are used to isolate the FC from vibrations rising from the main frame, as shown in Fig.2. This technique, which is referred to as "soft mounting" significantly reduces high-frequency mechanical noise.

As detailed in Fig.2, the mounting assembly sequence forms a layering structure. The structure contains screw head, washer, top O-ring, washer, perfboard, washer, Bottom O-ring, washer, spacer, washer, main frame, and a nut. Washers are interleaved to distribute the clamping force evenly across the O-ring, ensuring that they act as a damper, effectively reducing high-frequency vibrations.

Fig. 2. Soft mounting for vibration isolation featuring a dual O-ring structure.

2) *Barometer Shielding*: The barometric pressure sensor is highly sensitive to pressure fluctuations generated by propeller wash and aerodynamic disturbances generated during high-speed flight. These pressure fluctuations are directly linked to noise in altitude measuring.

To mitigate this, the barometer is placed under a piece of small open-cell foam, as shown in Fig.3. This blocks dynamic pressure spikes while allowing static atmospheric pressure to be measured accurately. The numerical validation of the shielding effect is provided in Section VI.

3) *Strategic Wiring*: To reduce EMI and ensure signal integrity, high current or critical communication line wiring is connected while twisted together. This technique effectively cancels out electromagnetic fields generated along the wire. By minimizing this interference, it also helps achieve signal integrity which is significantly important for high-speed communication or noise-sensitive sensors.

Regarding the hand-wired prototype built on a perfboard, critical signal paths are connected with minimal length to reduce noise and crosstalk.

Fig. 3. Barometer shielding constructed from open-cell foam.

III. REAL-TIME FIRMWARE ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 4. **Layered firmware architecture.** The system is structured into four distinct layers. Implementation of custom bare-metal drivers in the Driver Layer is to ensure real-time performance and allow transparent low-level hardware control.

A. Overview of Firmware Architecture

This section contains the overall firmware architecture design of the FC. The firmware for the FC adopts a hybrid bare-metal/RTOS architecture that combines the efficiency of bare-metal drivers with the task scheduling capability of the RTOS.

As shown in Fig. 4, the firmware is structured into four distinct layers.

- **Application Layer:** Contains the high-level logic for the flight itself, which is separated into execution tasks and mathematical algorithms.
- **Middleware Layer:** FreeRTOS Kernel is utilized for task scheduling and inter-task synchronization.
- **Driver Layer:** Implements custom bare-metal drivers through direct register manipulation. These drivers are optimized by using a few methods: Direct memory access (DMA), hardware interrupts, and efficient bus management strategies.
- **Hardware Layer:** Represents the hardware architecture detailed in Section II.

In addition, the Eigen library is used for complex matrix computations required by the ESKF algorithm.

The execution and scheduling are operated by the FreeRTOS scheduler based on a priority hierarchy. Fig. 5 presents the multi-rate task execution and its specific data flow. The whole system is centered around the Integrated Control Task, which operates at a 1kHz deterministic rate. This task is assigned as the highest priority task to preempt any other tasks, regardless

Fig. 5. **Multi-rate task execution and data flow diagram.** Tasks are classified by execution priority (Critical, High, Mid, Low) based on their real-time constraints and loop frequencies.

of their execution state. The detailed data flow inside the task and the inter-task synchronization are discussed in subsequent sections.

B. Driver Layer Implementation

This section details the implementation of the bare-metal driver layer and its important techniques.

1) **System Initialization:** Before real-time task execution starts, the MCU executes a system initialization sequence. The goal of this sequence is to configure the core, clock tree, interrupt, and peripherals into a deterministic state ready for proper flight operations.

After the MCU powers up, a hardware power-on reset forces the program counter (PC) to point to the reset vector address. Consequently, the MCU executes a startup routine that is defined in the startup assembly file. This allows the stack pointer to be initialized and executes `SystemInit()` before entering `main()`, as shown in Listing 1.

```

1 Reset_Handler:
2   ldr r0, =_estack
3   mov sp, r0
4   bl SystemInit
5   bl __libc_init_array
6   bl main

```

Listing 1. Reset Handler

Inside `SystemInit()`, the essential configuration is established. The 8MHz high-speed external (HSE) crystal is enabled and serves as the entry for the phased locked loop (PLL). The PLL is programmed to boost the system core clock to its maximum speed of 168MHz. After the PLL is programmed, the bus prescalers for the advanced high performance bus (AHB) and the advanced peripheral bus (APB) are configured. The power interface is also enabled for stable use of the maximum clock speed (168MHz).

To enable the ART accelerator for 0-wait state program execution, the flash wait state is adjusted, then the I-cache and D-cache are enabled.

Given the computational intensity of the algorithms utilized, the floating-point unit (FPU) is enabled. This is achieved by granting full access to the coprocessors CP10 and CP11 through the coprocessor access control register (CPACR).

After this core configuration, the firmware proceeds to configure the peripherals, which are used in the low-level drivers.

2) *Sensor Data Acquisition*: Sensor data acquisitions are designed to effectively acquire data with minimum CPU intervention while retaining a simple structure.

Sensors that have high ODR or sends large amounts of data communicate with the help of DMA. Components like the RF module, the GNSS module, and the IMU, transfers data by DMA with minimum CPU involvement. After DMA completes the data transfer, the corresponding interrupt handler notifies the relevant task, which is then executed. The 1kHz Integrated Control Task reads IMU data directly from the DMA buffer, while GNSS Task and RF Task also read directly from their DMA buffer. This method reduces wait loops in the driver layer, which frees up more CPU resources for ESKF estimation or control algorithms.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, both barometer and magnetometer share the same I2C interface line. Instead of utilizing two I2C interface lines, a single line that has access to both sensors is implemented. While this method is not suitable for high ODR sensors, the low speed of 20Hz and 25Hz loop rates makes it irrelevant. Rather, a benefit is gained by minimizing the physical pins used while maintaining stable communication.

The GNSS module is configured to send binary messages according to the UBX protocol. UART and DMA are used to fill the circular buffer with raw data, which are then parsed into a form that can be utilized by the ESKF algorithm. The data is parsed by a custom finite state machine (FSM) parser. Each of the received byte triggers a transition of the current state through a predefined set of states (SYNC1 → SYNC2 → CLASS → ID → LENGTH → PAYLOAD → CHECKSUM), allowing reliable data processing and optimized performance.

3) *DShot600 Actuation Driver*: Implementing a DShot600 actuation driver requires strict timing constraints. A software bit-banging approach, to generate the actual waveform, is unsuitable for a real-time FC. For DShot600, each bit period is $1.67\mu s$, and a single frame contains 16-bits. An actuation driver that updates four motors sequentially would keep the CPU busy for roughly $107\mu s$. Even if all four motors are updated in a parallel mechanism, the CPU must be kept busy for roughly $27\mu s$, which is a risk considering the blocking time in a 1kHz real-time control loop. However, with the DMA Burst based approach, the CPU is only used for the preparation of the DShot600 frames and triggering the DMA transfer. The actual waveform generation then proceeds by hardware without any CPU intervention, which frees up the CPU for other tasks.

Fig. 6 illustrates the internal workflow of the actuation driver. As described, the processing flow is separated into two distinct areas: a CPU intervention area, where the DShot600 frame is constructed and transformed into a hardware-ready form, and an autonomous operation area, where the actual pulse width modulation (PWM) signal is sent solely by the timer and DMA controller without any CPU involvement.

Fig. 6. **Processing flow of the DShot600 actuation driver.** The workflow is separated into two sections. CPU involved frame preparation and hardware autonomous waveform transmission.

CPU-side processing occurs inside the 1kHz Integrated Control Task, which first computes the desired thrust for each motor, and then constructs the corresponding 16-bit frame, each containing an 11-bit throttle value, a 1-bit telemetry request, and a 4-bit CRC, as illustrated in Fig. 7a. These constructed frames are then passed down to the DShot encoder, which converts every bit into its corresponding PWM capture compare register (CCR) value. Because DShot600 represents the logical '1' and '0' using different duty cycle patterns, the encoder generates a contiguous memory buffer that contains the corresponding CCR value for each bit written.

To allow the DMA Burst to transfer the data into four channels, the driver constructs a single unified contiguous buffer containing the CCR values of all motor outputs in sequence (motor 1 → motor 2 → motor 3 → motor 4). The

(a) DShot600 frame structure.

(b) DMA source buffer structure.

Fig. 7. **Data structure for DShot600 waveform generation.** The logical 16-bit frame from (a) are converted to their corresponding CCR value, then are interleaved and mapped into the unified contiguous buffer in (b), enabling autonomous waveform generation via DMA Burst.

detailed structure is shown in Fig. 7b. This eliminates the need for reconfiguring the DMA stream between motors, and enables the DMA Burst to update all channels without any CPU intervention.

A practical problem arises at the end of each frame. If the CCR value produced by the final DShot frame bit remains applied, the timer output would continue generating a non-zero duty cycle, which will lead to injecting unintended signals to the ESC. To prevent this, the encoder appends two zero CCR values after every 16-bit frame, forcing an idle interval before the next actuation command. Consequently, the encoder constructs a contiguous buffer of $4 \times (16+2) = 72$ CCR values.

Once this buffer is ready, the CPU triggers the DMA and runs other tasks. From this moment, the actual waveform transmission becomes fully autonomous. The timer creates a periodic update event (UDE), which causes the DMA controller to write the next CCR value directly into the four timer channels. This hardware-driven loop produces an accurate DShot600 waveform without any CPU involvement. After the transmission is complete, the timer output settles to the low state due to the appended CCR value that has been added at the end.

Ultimately, the CPU performs only the frame preparation while the timer and DMA controller guarantees precise and jitter-free actuation timing. This separation of responsibilities ensures that the 1kHz Integrated Control Task remains undisturbed and that the actuation is performed deterministically.

4) *Interrupt Handling:* In real-time embedded systems, the execution of complex logic or computationally intense operations directly within the interrupt service routine (ISR) can cause a blocking of lower-priority interrupts (i.e., those with numerically larger priority values) and distortion of FreeRTOS task scheduling. These issues all lead to an increase in interrupt latency and ultimately break the deterministic timing required for a robust real-time system.

To avoid this problem, all ISRs in the system are designed to minimize its execution time. Strict limitations are placed on the actions that could be taken inside the ISR: clearing interrupt flags, updating timestamps or buffer indexes, and notifying a related task via `vTaskNotifyGiveFromISR`.

All computationally intense operations are yielded to the FreeRTOS tasks, where they can be scheduled deterministically. For instance, in the IMU data-ready ISR, only the current timestamp acquisition and a task notification are executed. The actual IMU data parsing, post-processing, and scaling all occur inside the 1kHz Integrated Control Task. Similarly, the DMA completion ISR merely disables the DMA and notifies the related task without any post-processing.

By minimizing the time spent inside the ISR, the firmware ensures predictable task scheduling, reduces interrupt latency, and improves its responsiveness.

C. Middleware

The middleware layer serves as a bridge between the driver layer and the application layer, which allows the real-time execution of the whole system. In this section, the internal

behavior of the task or the data flow between them is not discussed. Those will be detailed in Section III-D. Instead, this section will focus on the FreeRTOS Kernel configuration and task priorities that enable deterministic task scheduling.

1) *FreeRTOS Configuration:*

Preemptive Scheduling: By enabling preemptive scheduling, higher-priority tasks can immediately preempt currently running lower-priority tasks. This behavior is essential for meeting the hard real-time requirements of the 1kHz Integrated Control Task, which must be executed with minimal jitter and latency. Preemption ensures that a critical task is never delayed by any other non-critical tasks.

Static Memory Allocation: FreeRTOS provides two ways for creating RTOS objects: dynamic allocation and static allocation. In this system, every object is created exclusively with static allocation. This is essential for time-sensitive embedded systems, where heap fragmentation or allocation failures must be strictly avoided. The use of static allocation ensures that the memory consumption is fixed and known at compile time, thereby improving robustness, determinism, and overall predictability of the system.

Tick Rate: FreeRTOS has an internal periodic system tick that manages time-based mechanisms such as task delays, timeouts, and timers. The tick rate is set to 1kHz in this system, which is equivalent to a tick period of 1ms.

It is important to note that this configured tick rate does not determine how frequently tasks can be executed. Instead, it defines only the timing resolution of the FreeRTOS Kernel's scheduling and delay functions. Event driven context switches such as those that are executed by interrupts or DMA completions can occur at a much higher rate regardless of the tick rate.

Although increasing the tick rate might appear beneficial due to its higher nominal resolution, higher tick frequencies significantly increase overhead and CPU usage, providing no practical benefit for the real-time system.

Port Optimized Task Selection: This feature allows the scheduler to choose the highest priority ready task in constant time ($O(1)$) by using architecture specific assembly instructions such as the Count Leading Zeros (CLZ). As the ARMv7-M architecture supports this instruction, port optimized task selection is enabled in this system, resulting in faster context switching. Although this feature limits the maximum number of task priorities to 32, it is irrelevant in this system, as the total number of tasks is less than 10.

Interrupt and System Call Priority: FreeRTOS requires a strict guideline for interrupt priorities to ensure correct and deterministic FreeRTOS Kernel operation. Two configuration parameters are crucial for this guideline: `configKERNEL_INTERRUPT_PRIORITY` (hereafter referred to as `KERNEL_PRIO`), which defines the lowest interrupt priority used by the kernel, and `configMAX_SYSCALL_INTERRUPT_PRIORITY` (hereafter referred to as `MAX_SYSCALL`), which defines the highest interrupt priority from which the interrupt safe FreeRTOS API functions can be called.

For Cortex-M4 processor cores, all interrupt priorities are stored in the Nested Vectored Interrupt Controller’s (NVIC) 8-bit Interrupt Priority Register (IPR). However, only the upper `configPRIO_BITS` are implemented in hardware. Since STM32F405 implements a 4-bit priority field, `configPRIO_BITS` must be configured as 4. As a result, priority values are left-aligned by a shift operation to match the proper mapping of the priority.

It is important to distinguish between the priority conventions used by NVIC and FreeRTOS task scheduling.

- In the NVIC, higher priority means lower numeric priority value.
- In FreeRTOS task scheduling, higher priority represents a higher numeric priority value.

Interrupts whose NVIC priority is numerically greater than or equal to `MAX_SYSCALL` and numerically lower than or equal to `KERNEL_PRIO` may safely call ‘FromISR’ API functions inside the ISR. Conversely, interrupts whose priority is numerically lower than (i.e., logically higher priority) `MAX_SYSCALL` must not call any FreeRTOS API functions, as they operate outside the kernel-managed area.

FPU: As the FPU is enabled at the MCU level, enabling FPU support in FreeRTOS is mandatory to ensure data integrity during context switching.

Overall, these configurations ensure that FreeRTOS provides a deterministic and robust real-time environment for the system.

2) *Task Priority:* The priority values listed in Table III describes the FreeRTOS task scheduling priorities.

D. Application Layer

The application layer defines the execution logic of all high-level algorithms and flight tasks within the FC. While the mathematical details of the ESKF and control algorithms are to be discussed in later sections, this section focuses on their operational behavior: how ISRs trigger task execution, how global variables are handled safely without concurrent access, and how the internal workflow of each task is organized.

1) *Synchronization via Event Triggering and Shared Data Handling:* For task synchronization, an event-driven task execution via task notification is utilized, which allows external interrupts to trigger tasks with ease inside the ISR. This ensures deterministic and low-latency wake-up behavior for time critical tasks.

TABLE III
FREERTOS TASK PRIORITIES.

Priority	Task	Execution Trigger	Target Rate
9	Integrated Control Task	Event-driven	1kHz
8	ESKF Core Task	Periodic	200Hz
7	Outer Control Task	Periodic	100Hz
6	RF Task	Event-driven	≈100Hz
5	GNSS Task	Event-driven	≈5Hz
4	Barometer Task	Periodic	20Hz
3	Magnetometer Task	Periodic	25Hz

Shared variables between tasks can cause a concurrency problem when accessed simultaneously, which leads to a violation of data consistency. To mitigate this, a mutex is used to protect the shared variables. A task acquires a mutex before entering a critical section, updating or reading states, then releases the mutex. This section must be kept short for deterministic task scheduling.

These two synchronization methods lay the foundation for real-time execution of the application layer. Next, using these methods, the internal workflow of each task is described in detail.

2) Internal Workflow of Individual Tasks:

Integrated Control Task: This task is the highest frequency task in the system, triggered by the IMU data-ready interrupt through a task notification. Upon activation, the task initiates a DMA-based IMU read and waits for the DMA completion event. During this transfer period, the scheduler yields execution to other tasks for efficiency. Once the latest IMU data becomes available, the task acquires the ‘state mutex’, performs the ESKF prediction, and retrieves a snapshot of the current state. It then computes the torque for each motor via Quaternion PD Control (utilizing data from the Outer Control Task, which is acquired using ‘control mutex’) and motor mixing, which is then forwarded to the DShot600 actuation driver. Keeping the state prediction and inner-loop control within a single event-driven task minimizes sensor to actuation latency and ensures stable timing behavior.

ESKF Core Task: This task runs at a periodic rate of 200Hz and performs the update step of the ESKF. At the beginning of each cycle, the task acquires the ‘state mutex’ and captures a snapshot of the current state and IMU data, which are calculated in the Integrated Control Task. It then checks for newly arrived sensor data such as GNSS, barometer, and magnetometer. After the computation of the ESKF covariance matrix, it executes the ESKF update corresponding to the available sensor type.

Outer Control Task: This task runs at a periodic rate of 100Hz and computes the desired values that will be used by the Integrated Control Task. At the start of each cycle, the task acquires the ‘state mutex’ and retrieves a snapshot of the current state. Using this snapshot, the task executes the outer loop control algorithm to generate the desired attitude, rate, and base thrust. These values are saved to a shared buffer protected by the ‘control mutex’, ensuring data consistency.

RF Task: This task follows an event-driven task execution similar to the Integrated Control Task. It is triggered by an RF data-ready interrupt through a task notification. Then it initiates a DMA-based reception and waits for the DMA completion event. Once the data is available, it is post-processed and written to a shared control buffer with the latest control values. This data is later consumed by the Outer Control Task.

GNSS, Barometer, Magnetometer Tasks: These low rate sensing tasks follow a straightforward execution flow. Each task is triggered either periodically (barometer, magnetometer) or by a DMA completion interrupt (GNSS). After acquiring new sensor data, post-processing is performed, and the result

is written into a corresponding sensor buffer. A sensor update flag is then set to indicate the ESKF Core Task that a new sensor data is available.

Since the barometer and magnetometer share the same I2C bus, a mutex is utilized to prevent bus collision. In addition, during each sensor's conversion period, the task remains blocked, allowing other tasks to be executed efficiently.

IV. STATE ESTIMATION AND SENSOR FUSION

Accurate state estimation is essential for achieving stable flight control. The Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF) is utilized to estimate the quadrotor UAV's position, velocity, attitude, and angular velocity by fusing measurements from IMU, GNSS, barometer, and magnetometer. This section begins by introducing the coordinate frames and conventions used in the formulation, followed by the modeling and implementation details.

The formulation used in this system follows the standard model of the ESKF introduced by Solà [1], with additional adjustments and extensions. The full derivation of the standard ESKF model can be found in [1].

A. Coordinate Frames and Conventions

1) *Reference Frames*: To describe the kinematics and dynamics of the quadrotor UAV, two right-handed coordinate frames are defined: the world frame and the body frame, which is illustrated in Fig. 8. These frames provide the basis for expressing the overall motion of the quadrotor UAV.

- **World Frame F_W** : The North-East-Down (NED) frame is a right-handed Cartesian coordinate frame defined on a local tangent plane, fixed to a specific point on the Earth's surface. The positive X-axis points toward the north, the positive Y-axis points toward the east, and the positive Z-axis points downward, towards the center of the Earth, which is aligned with the gravitational direction. Accordingly, the gravity vector is defined as $\mathbf{g} = [0 \ 0 \ g]^\top$, where $g \approx 9.81\text{m/s}^2$. This frame serves as a reference for expressing the global position, velocity, and attitude.
- **Body Frame F_B** : The Forward-Right-Down (FRD) frame is a body-fixed coordinate frame whose origin lies at the vehicle's center of mass. The positive X-axis points forward, the positive Y-axis points to the right, and the positive Z-axis points downward, to the bottom of the vehicle. IMU measurements are naturally expressed in this frame.

2) *Quaternions and Rotations*: Variations in conventions can lead to significant ambiguity in mathematical modeling and implementation. Thus, the conventions utilized must be explicitly defined.

Scalar-First Convention: A quaternion is written in scalar-first form as

$$\mathbf{q} = [q_w \ q_x \ q_y \ q_z]^\top,$$

where q_w is the scalar part and $\mathbf{q}_v = [q_x \ q_y \ q_z]^\top$ is the vector part.

(a) North-East-Down (NED) frame.

(b) Forward-Right-Down (FRD) frame.

Fig. 8. **Definitions of reference frames.** (a) The world frame follows the North-East-Down (NED) frame. (b) The body frame follows the Forward-Right-Down (FRD) frame, with the origin placed at the vehicle's center of mass.

Hamilton Convention: The Hamilton convention is used for the multiplication of imaginary units.

$$i^2 = j^2 = k^2 = ijk = -1$$

Quaternion Product and Matrix Form: For the quaternion product, the \otimes operator is used. The product of two quaternions is defined as

$$\mathbf{p} \otimes \mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} p_w q_w - \mathbf{p}_v^\top \mathbf{q}_v \\ p_w \mathbf{q}_v + q_w \mathbf{p}_v + \mathbf{p}_v \times \mathbf{q}_v \end{bmatrix}.$$

Since the quaternion product is non-commutative, the order of its multiplication matters. If a rotation \mathbf{q}_1 is applied before \mathbf{q}_2 , the final composed rotation is defined as

$$\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_2 \otimes \mathbf{q}_1.$$

For the quaternion product, the left-multiplication convention is applied as

$$\mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{p} = [\mathbf{q}]_L \mathbf{p},$$

where $[\mathbf{q}]_L$ is defined as

$$[\mathbf{q}]_L = q_w \mathbf{I}_4 + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{q}_v^\top \\ \mathbf{q}_v & [\mathbf{q}_v]_\times \end{bmatrix}.$$

$[\mathbf{v}]_\times$ in this equation denotes the skew-symmetric matrix of the vector \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{I}_4 is the identity matrix.

Rotation Matrix Convention: The rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{WB} \in SO(3)$ represents a passive coordinate transformation that maps a vector expressed in the body frame F_B into the world frame F_W . For a vector expressed in F_B , its representation in F_W can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{v}_W = \mathbf{R}_{WB} \mathbf{v}_B.$$

Using this convention, the physical vector itself remains stationary, while its coordinates are re-expressed in a different frame. This convention is used throughout the system. The inverse transformation, which represents a direction from the world frame to the body frame is given by transpose.

$$\mathbf{R}_{BW} = \mathbf{R}_{WB}^\top$$

Quaternion Frame Transformation: Similarly, the quaternion q_{WB} represents the orientation of the body frame with respect to the world frame. A vector \mathbf{v}_B expressed in the body frame can be transformed into the coordinates in the world frame using

$$\mathbf{v}_W = \mathbf{q}_{WB} \otimes \mathbf{v}_B \otimes \mathbf{q}_{WB}^*$$

where \mathbf{v}_B denotes the corresponding pure quaternion $[0 \ \mathbf{v}_B^\top]^\top$ for the calculation.

3) Notations and Definitions:

Notational Conventions: Throughout this paper, scalars are denoted as non-bold letters (e.g., q_w), and quaternions, vectors, and matrices are denoted as bold letters (e.g., \mathbf{v}). The hat notation is used to denote an estimated value (e.g., $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$).

Skew-Symmetric Matrix: The skew-symmetric matrix operator $[\cdot]_\times$ maps a vector $\mathbf{v} = [v_x, v_y, v_z]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ to a matrix in $\mathfrak{so}(3)$, defined as

$$[\mathbf{v}]_\times = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -v_z & v_y \\ v_z & 0 & -v_x \\ -v_y & v_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

This operator represents cross products as matrix multiplications ($\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b} = [\mathbf{a}]_\times \mathbf{b}$).

State Definitions: The ESKF algorithm uses two distinct core state definitions which explains the true state of the system (true state = nominal state \oplus error state): the nominal state \mathbf{x} and the error state $\delta\mathbf{x}$.

The nominal state represents the nonlinear estimate of the system obtained from the IMU data, which does not include any model imperfections such as noise and perturbations. Its 22-state is defined as

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{q} \\ \mathbf{a}_b \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \\ \mathbf{m}_b \\ \mathbf{m}_{world} \end{bmatrix}_{22 \times 1}.$$

$\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Position in the world frame.
$\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Velocity in the world frame.
$\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{S}^3, \ \mathbf{q}\ = 1$	Unit quaternion representing the orientation of the body frame respect to the world frame.
$\mathbf{a}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Accelerometer bias in the body frame.
$\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Gyroscope bias in the body frame.
$\mathbf{m}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Magnetometer bias in the body frame.
$\mathbf{m}_{world} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Local Earth magnetic field in the world frame.

The error state represents the small errors between the true state and the nominal state, under a linearized dynamic system. Its 21-state is defined as

$$\delta\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta\mathbf{p} \\ \delta\mathbf{v} \\ \delta\boldsymbol{\theta} \\ \delta\mathbf{a}_b \\ \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \\ \delta\mathbf{m}_b \\ \delta\mathbf{m}_{world} \end{bmatrix}_{21 \times 1}.$$

$\delta\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Position error in the world frame.
$\delta\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Velocity error in the world frame.
$\delta\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Orientation error between the true and nominal quaternion, expressed in the body frame.
$\delta\mathbf{a}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Accelerometer bias error in the body frame.
$\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Gyroscope bias error in the body frame.
$\delta\mathbf{m}_b \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Magnetometer bias error in the body frame.
$\delta\mathbf{m}_{world} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Local earth magnetic field error in the world frame.

Noise Definitions: The ESKF algorithm distinguishes two types of noises: a measurement noise which is the uncertainty of the sensor reading, and a process noise which is the uncertainty of the system model.

Measurement noise:	
$\sigma_{\mathbf{a}_n}$	Accelerometer measurement noise standard deviation.
$\sigma_{\boldsymbol{\omega}_n}$	Gyroscope measurement noise standard deviation.
σ_{b_n}	Barometer measurement noise standard deviation.
$\sigma_{\mathbf{m}_n}$	Magnetometer measurement noise standard deviation.
σ_{pos, h_n}	GNSS horizontal position measurement noise standard deviation.
σ_{pos, v_n}	GNSS vertical position measurement noise standard deviation.
σ_{vel_n}	GNSS velocity measurement noise standard deviation.
Process noise:	
$\sigma_{\mathbf{a}_w}$	Accelerometer bias random walk noise standard deviation.
$\sigma_{\boldsymbol{\omega}_w}$	Gyroscope bias random walk noise standard deviation.
$\sigma_{\mathbf{m}_w}$	Magnetometer bias random walk noise standard deviation.
$\sigma_{\mathbf{m}_{world, w}}$	World magnetic field bias random walk noise standard deviation.

B. System Kinematics Modeling

The ESKF formulation is built upon three core kinematic models which are all defined in continuous time: the true-state kinematics, the nominal-state kinematics, and the error-state kinematics. In addition, low-rate sensor measurement models (e.g., GNSS, barometer, and magnetometer) are incorporated to enable the filter update step.

1) *True State Kinematics*: The continuous time kinematics of the true state \mathbf{x}_t is denoted as $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_t$, which is governed by the IMU measurements and the noise elements. The true state \mathbf{x}_t itself is expressed as a composition of the nominal state \mathbf{x} and the error state $\delta\mathbf{x}$ as

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{x} \oplus \delta\mathbf{x}.$$

It is important to note that the "true state" used here, is not the physical absolute truth state. Instead, it is a mathematical construct defined within the filter that should be interpreted as a conceptual model, not as the real physical state.

The following formulation describes the kinematics of the true state in continuous time.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{p}}_t &= \mathbf{v}_t \\ \dot{\mathbf{v}}_t &= \mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}_t\}(\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_{bt} - \mathbf{a}_n) + \mathbf{g} \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}}_t &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{q}_t \otimes (\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_{bt} - \boldsymbol{\omega}_n) \\ \dot{\mathbf{a}}_{bt} &= \mathbf{a}_w \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{bt} &= \boldsymbol{\omega}_w \\ \dot{\mathbf{m}}_{bt} &= \mathbf{m}_w \\ \dot{\mathbf{m}}_{world,t} &= \mathbf{m}_{world,w}\end{aligned}$$

\mathbf{a}_m and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_m$ represent the sensor measurements of the IMU, and the following \mathbf{a}_n and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_n$ represent the sensor measurement noise. The $\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}$ denotes the rotation matrix produced by the quaternion.

The magnetometer bias \mathbf{m}_b and the local Earth magnetic field \mathbf{m}_{world} are added as a state variable, differentiating from the standard model. Although the filter is initialized with calibrated hard iron distortion values which are theoretically constant, the actual magnetometer bias varies within flight due to thermal drift of the MEMS sensor and external EMI. Therefore, magnetometer bias is modeled as a random walk process within the state vector, enabling continuous compensation of disturbances and improving the accuracy and stability of yaw estimation.

Similarly, relying on a fixed initial estimate of the reference local magnetic field may lead to yaw estimation errors in environments where the local magnetic field is distorted (e.g., near iron bridges or urban areas). By modeling \mathbf{m}_{world} as a random walk process, the filter can adapt its internal estimate of the local magnetic field to match the actual environmental variations. This enables the quadrotor UAV to maintain robust yaw estimation even in magnetic disturbance environments.

The gravity vector \mathbf{g} is treated as a constant vector $[0 \ 0 \ 9.80665]^\top$ in the world frame instead of estimating the gravity vector as a state variable, which is a more classical approach mentioned in [1]. Implementing the initialization procedure that yields the accurate initial attitude and magnetic field, reducing the initial uncertainty, provides filter stability upon startup and enables flight from uneven terrain. This also allows the reduction of the state dimension, reducing the computation complexity.

2) *Nominal State Kinematics*: The continuous time kinematics of the nominal state \mathbf{x} conform to the true state kinematics without any noise or perturbations. All noise and perturbations are handled in the error state kinematics, while the nominal state kinematics covers a noise-free ideal system model. The kinematics of the nominal state in continuous time is formulated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{p}} &= \mathbf{v} \\ \dot{\mathbf{v}} &= \mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}(\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b) + \mathbf{g} \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{q} \otimes (\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_b) \\ \dot{\mathbf{a}}_b &= 0 \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b &= 0 \\ \dot{\mathbf{m}}_b &= 0 \\ \dot{\mathbf{m}}_{world} &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Regarding the nominal state kinematics, the derivatives of the biases and the local magnetic field are assumed to be zero, since the derivatives are modeled by the zero-mean white Gaussian noise.

3) *Error State Kinematics*: The continuous time error state kinematics describes the linear dynamics of the state errors, based on the small error assumption. The following formulation describes the error state kinematics.

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\dot{\mathbf{p}} &= \delta\mathbf{v} \\ \delta\dot{\mathbf{v}} &= -\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}[\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b]_{\times} - \mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}\delta\mathbf{a}_b - \mathbf{a}_n \\ \delta\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}} &= -[\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_b]_{\times}\delta\boldsymbol{\theta} - \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b - \boldsymbol{\omega}_n \\ \delta\dot{\mathbf{a}}_b &= \mathbf{a}_w \\ \delta\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b &= \boldsymbol{\omega}_w \\ \delta\dot{\mathbf{m}}_b &= \mathbf{m}_w \\ \delta\dot{\mathbf{m}}_{world} &= \mathbf{m}_{world,w}\end{aligned}$$

Compared to the standard model, the gravity vector is treated as a constant and has been removed from the state vector, which causes the corresponding gravity error term $\delta\mathbf{g}$ not to appear in the error state kinematics.

4) *Measurement Models*: To correct the accumulated errors from the ESKF state prediction, the system uses low-rate exteroceptive sensors such as a GNSS module, a barometer, and a magnetometer. Each measurement follows the general model, which is defined as

$$\mathbf{y} = h(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}.$$

Here, \mathbf{y} is the actual sensor measurement. $h(\cdot)$ is the sensor-specific measurement function and \mathbf{v} is the measurement noise, which is a zero-mean white Gaussian noise.

GNSS Measurement Model: The GNSS module provides position and velocity expressed in the world (NED) frame.

$$\begin{aligned}h_{gnss}(\mathbf{x}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{v} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{y}_{gnss} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{gnss,p} \\ \mathbf{y}_{gnss,v} \end{bmatrix} = h_{gnss}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_{gnss}\end{aligned}$$

The position measurement in \mathbf{y}_{gnss} is represented as the relative position to the initial reference position after converting the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) into the local NED frame.

Barometer Measurement Model: The barometer provides an altitude derived from the pressure measurement.

$$\begin{aligned} h_{baro}(\mathbf{x}) &= -p_z \\ \mathbf{y}_{baro} &= h_{baro}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_{baro} \end{aligned}$$

The measurement \mathbf{y}_{baro} represents the altitude relative to the reference altitude of the initial reference pressure level. Since the barometer altitude increases upward and the NED frame defines the positive Z-axis as downward, the measurement function is modeled as the negative of the vertical position.

Magnetometer Measurement Model: The magnetometer provides the local magnetic field expressed in the body frame.

$$\begin{aligned} h_{mag}(\mathbf{x}) &= (\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\})^\top \mathbf{m}_{world} + \mathbf{m}_b \\ \mathbf{y}_{mag} &= h_{mag}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_{mag} \end{aligned}$$

The $\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}^\top \mathbf{m}_{world}$ represents the local Earth magnetic field transformed from the world frame to the body frame, and \mathbf{m}_b is the magnetometer bias including hard iron distortions and other slowly drifting biases.

C. ESKF Prediction

The ESKF prediction step evolves both the nominal state and the error covariance using high-frequency IMU measurements.

1) *Discretization of the System Kinematics:* For practical implementation on a digital processor, the continuous time kinematic models must be discretized using the time step Δt . Euler method is applied for integration. The discrete time kinematics for the nominal state are written as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p} &\leftarrow \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{v}\Delta t + \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}(\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b) + \mathbf{g})\Delta t^2 \\ \mathbf{v} &\leftarrow \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}(\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b) + \mathbf{g})\Delta t \\ \mathbf{q} &\leftarrow \mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{q}\{(\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_b)\Delta t\} \\ \mathbf{a}_b &\leftarrow \mathbf{a}_b \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_b &\leftarrow \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \\ \mathbf{m}_b &\leftarrow \mathbf{m}_b \\ \mathbf{m}_{world} &\leftarrow \mathbf{m}_{world} \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\mathbf{q}\{\mathbf{v}\}$ denotes the quaternion corresponding to the rotation vector \mathbf{v} , and $\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}$ is the rotation matrix associated with the quaternion \mathbf{q} .

The following formulation describes the error state kinematics in discrete time.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\mathbf{p} &\leftarrow \delta\mathbf{p} + \delta\mathbf{v}\Delta t \\ \delta\mathbf{v} &\leftarrow \delta\mathbf{v} + (-\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}[\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b] \times \delta\boldsymbol{\theta} - \mathbf{R}\delta\mathbf{a}_b)\Delta t + \mathbf{v}_i \\ \delta\boldsymbol{\theta} &\leftarrow (\mathbf{R}\{(\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_b)\Delta t\})^\top \delta\boldsymbol{\theta} - \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b\Delta t + \boldsymbol{\theta}_i \\ \delta\mathbf{a}_b &\leftarrow \delta\mathbf{a}_b + \mathbf{a}_i \\ \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b &\leftarrow \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}_b + \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \\ \delta\mathbf{m}_b &\leftarrow \delta\mathbf{m}_b + \mathbf{m}_i \\ \delta\mathbf{m}_{world} &\leftarrow \delta\mathbf{m}_{world} + \mathbf{m}_{world,i} \end{aligned}$$

The term \mathbf{v}_i , $\boldsymbol{\theta}_i$, \mathbf{a}_i , $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$, \mathbf{m}_i , and $\mathbf{m}_{world,i}$ represent the zero-mean Gaussian random impulses for velocity, orientation, biases, and local magnetic field.

2) *Definition of Jacobian and Covariance Matrices:* The error state system is expressed as

$$\delta\mathbf{x} \leftarrow f(\mathbf{x}, \delta\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_m, \mathbf{i}) = \mathbf{F}_x(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_m)\delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{F}_i\mathbf{i},$$

where term \mathbf{x} is the nominal state vector, $\delta\mathbf{x}$ is the error state vector, \mathbf{u}_m is the input vector, and \mathbf{i} is the perturbation impulses vector as mentioned in [1]. \mathbf{u}_m and \mathbf{i} are defined as

$$\mathbf{u}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_m \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_m \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{i} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_i \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}_i \\ \mathbf{a}_i \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \\ \mathbf{m}_i \\ \mathbf{m}_{world,i} \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure. 9 presents the block forms of \mathbf{F}_x , \mathbf{F}_i , and \mathbf{Q}_i , which are used for computing the prediction step.

3) *Filter Prediction:* The filter prediction step starts with the prediction of the nominal state using the discrete time nominal state kinematics introduced previously. Then the prediction of the error state and covariance is performed as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\delta\mathbf{x}} &\leftarrow \mathbf{F}_x\hat{\delta\mathbf{x}} \\ \mathbf{P} &\leftarrow \mathbf{F}_x\mathbf{P}\mathbf{F}_x^\top + \mathbf{F}_i\mathbf{Q}_i\mathbf{F}_i^\top. \end{aligned}$$

Since the error state $\hat{\delta\mathbf{x}}$ is reset to zero after the every ESKF update step, the first expression always returns 0. Therefore, only the second expression which is the covariance prediction, is required in the actual implementation.

D. ESKF Update

The ESKF update step corrects the error accumulated in the prediction step, using new measurement data from exteroceptive sensors.

The update step is formulated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K} &= \mathbf{P}\mathbf{H}^\top(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{H}^\top + \mathbf{V})^{-1} \\ \hat{\delta\mathbf{x}} &\leftarrow \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{y} - h(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t)) \\ \mathbf{P} &\leftarrow (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{H})\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{H})^\top + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{V}\mathbf{K}^\top \end{aligned}$$

As described in Solà's work [1], since the nominal state \mathbf{x} already represents the estimate of the true state at this stage

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{F}_x &= \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \delta \mathbf{x}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_m} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \Delta t & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}[\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_b]_x \Delta t & -\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\} \Delta t & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & (\mathbf{R}\{(\boldsymbol{\omega}_m - \boldsymbol{\omega}_b) \Delta t\})^\top & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \Delta t & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}_{21 \times 21} \\
\mathbf{F}_i &= \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{i}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_m} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ -\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}_{21 \times 18} \\
\mathbf{Q}_i &= \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{\mathbf{a}_n}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \sigma_{\boldsymbol{\omega}_n}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \sigma_{\mathbf{a}_w}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \sigma_{\boldsymbol{\omega}_w}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \sigma_{\mathbf{m}_w}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \sigma_{\mathbf{m}_{world,w}}^2 \Delta t^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}_{18 \times 18}
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 9. Block form representation of the Jacobian and covariance matrices used in the ESKF prediction.

(the error state mean being zero), the nominal state \mathbf{x} is used as the parameter of the measurement function $h(\cdot)$.

The Joseph form is adopted for the error covariance matrix \mathbf{P} update. Although more computation is required, it ensures a symmetric matrix form and prevents negative eigenvalues, improving the numerical stability.

After the computation of the error state and error covariance matrix, the error is injected into the nominal state as

$$\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x} \oplus \hat{\delta \mathbf{x}}.$$

The detailed injection formulations using the corresponding composition method, are demonstrated below.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{p} &\leftarrow \mathbf{p} + \hat{\delta \mathbf{p}} \\
\mathbf{v} &\leftarrow \mathbf{v} + \hat{\delta \mathbf{v}} \\
\mathbf{q} &\leftarrow \mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{q}\{\hat{\delta \boldsymbol{\theta}}\} \\
\mathbf{a}_b &\leftarrow \mathbf{a}_b + \hat{\delta \mathbf{a}}_b \\
\boldsymbol{\omega}_b &\leftarrow \boldsymbol{\omega}_b + \hat{\delta \boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \\
\mathbf{m}_b &\leftarrow \mathbf{m}_b + \hat{\delta \mathbf{m}}_b \\
\mathbf{m}_{world} &\leftarrow \mathbf{m}_{world} + \hat{\delta \mathbf{m}}_{world}
\end{aligned}$$

As the nominal state includes the error, after the error injection step, a reset must be executed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\delta \mathbf{x}} &\leftarrow \mathbf{0} \\
\mathbf{P} &\leftarrow \mathbf{GPG}^\top
\end{aligned}$$

Under the small angle assumption, this system approximates the matrix \mathbf{G} as a identity matrix $\mathbf{I}_{21 \times 21}$, which simplifies

the reset operation, ultimately leaving the covariance matrix \mathbf{P} unchanged.

To apply the general ESKF update step previously described, the Jacobian matrix \mathbf{H} and the measurement noise covariance matrix \mathbf{V} must be specified for each sensor. Note that the general update step is operated through these matrices and measurement models introduced earlier in Section IV-B.

GNSS Module:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{H}_{gnss} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \cdots \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \cdots \end{bmatrix}_{6 \times 21} \\
\mathbf{V}_{gnss} &= \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{pos,h_n}^2 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} \\ 0 & \sigma_{pos,h_n}^2 & 0 & \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{pos,v_n}^2 & \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} & \sigma_{vel_n}^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}_{6 \times 6} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} hAcc^2 \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 2} & vAcc^2 & \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 2} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} & sAcc^2 \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}_{6 \times 6}
\end{aligned}$$

The accuracy indicators provided from the GNSS (hAcc, vAcc, sAcc) represent the RMS error bounds of the position and velocity measurements.

- hAcc: Horizontal accuracy estimate
- vAcc: Vertical accuracy estimate
- sAcc: Speed accuracy estimate

Although these values are not practically statistical standard deviations, but can be recognized as such, under zero-mean white Gaussian noise circumstances. Therefore, the GNSS measurement covariance matrix is constructed directly from these accuracy indicators. It is important that these accuracy indicators vary at each measurement moment, allowing \mathbf{V}_{gnss}

to function as a dynamic covariance matrix that adapts to changing measurement uncertainties.

Since the GNSS provides direct measurements of both position and velocity, the Jacobian H_{gnss} contains identity matrices in the corresponding state locations within the matrix. The remaining states, such as bias errors and orientation errors, do not appear in the GNSS measurement data, and therefore the corresponding blocks appear as zero.

Barometer:

$$\mathbf{H}_{baro} = [0 \ 0 \ -1 \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots]_{1 \times 21}$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{baro} = \sigma_{b_n}^2$$

Since the barometer measures the altitude, which corresponds to the negative Z-axis of the position in the NED frame, the Jacobian \mathbf{H}_{baro} simply yields a row vector with a value of "-1" at the location corresponding to the vertical position state and zeros elsewhere.

Magnetometer:

$$\mathbf{H}_{mag} = [\mathbf{0}_{3 \times 6} \ [\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{m}_{world}]_\times \ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 6} \ \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \ \mathbf{R}^\top]_{3 \times 21}$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{mag} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{m_n}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{m_n}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{m_n}^2 \end{bmatrix}_{3 \times 3}$$

The rotation matrix \mathbf{R} used in this formulation denotes $\mathbf{R}\{\mathbf{q}\}$. The Jacobian \mathbf{H}_{mag} is obtained by linearizing the measurement model

$$h_{mag}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{m}_{world} + \mathbf{m}_b.$$

Using the small-angle approximation $\mathbf{R}_t \approx \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{I} + [\delta\theta]_\times)$, which leads to

$$\delta h = \dots + [\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{m}_{world}]_\times \delta\theta.$$

This results in the orientation error Jacobian term

$$[\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{m}_{world}]_\times.$$

The remaining blocks simply capture the direct relationship between the error state and the measurement of the magnetometer bias and local magnetic field.

E. ESKF Implementation Details

For a stable and robust real-time implementation, a number of considerations must be taken into account. This section describes the key implementation details applied in the system.

1) *Multi-Rate Prediction:* The theoretical formulation of the ESKF prediction step includes both the nominal state prediction and the covariance prediction, which occur at the same step. However, executing both prediction at an equivalent rate to the IMU ODR is computationally challenging. The covariance prediction involves matrix operations on dimensions as large as 21×21 , imposing a significant computational load on the MCU. According to the performance measurements, the covariance computation requires approximately 1.64ms, which exceeds the 1ms update period of the IMU. In contrast, the nominal state prediction takes about 9us.

Therefore, to meet real-time constraints, each prediction is executed at a different rate. The nominal state prediction is executed upon the arrival of every IMU measurement (1kHz) to ensure the real-time state estimation necessary for the high-speed control, while the covariance prediction is performed at a reduced rate of 200Hz. Although lower rate covariance prediction can lead to a slight delay in reflecting uncertainty growth, this effect is negligible since the actual uncertainty does not grow in a significant speed. Ultimately, this strategy maintains real-time performance while reducing the computational load on the MCU.

2) *System Initialization:* A reliable system initialization procedure is required to ensure stable filter operation during the initial phase. Since the ESKF is based on the small-error assumption, inaccuracies in the initial state can lead to rapid filter divergence. The initialization process is divided into three stages: data acquisition & pre-processing, initial nominal state computation, and covariance & reference setup.

Data Acquisition & Pre-processing: Both offline and online calibration parameters are required for the initialization of the system. Offline calibration data includes accelerometer offset and scale factors obtained from six-point calibration, and magnetometer hard iron and soft iron parameters obtained from the ellipsoid fitting method. Also, sensor sensitivity values from the sensor datasheet are used to convert raw measurements into physical units.

During the initial startup, the system undergoes a stationary initialization phase. During this period, IMU, barometer, magnetometer, and GNSS measurements are collected for a short period of time. These samples are averaged to reduce sensor noise and provide stable initial measurements of the sensors. These averaged values form the basis for estimating the initial nominal state and calculating the reference values for the altitude and position.

Initial Nominal State Computation: Using the pre-processed data, the nominal state is initialized. As the starting location is decided as the origin of the world (NED) frame, the position is set to zero. The velocity is also set to zero as the system assumes a stationary start. Gyroscope bias is initialized as the online averaged measurement, while the accelerometer and magnetometer biases are initialized by the offline calibration parameters, both applied with their sensor sensitivities and soft iron parameters.

The initial attitude is computed through the averaged accelerometer and the magnetometer measurements. Roll and pitch angles are obtained from the normalized accelerometer vector, and the yaw angle is computed by the tilt compensated magnetometer vector. These Euler angles are then converted into the initial quaternion attitude. Furthermore, the local Earth magnetic field state is initialized by converting the averaged magnetometer measurement into the world frame using the computed initial attitude.

Covariance & Reference Setup: The value of the error covariance matrix \mathbf{P} depends on the specific hardware characteristics. Even with identical sensor models, variations

in sensor noise, mounting, and wiring differentiate the ideal tuning value.

Although tuning values vary from system to system, the general tendency remains the same. For relatively reliable states such as roll and pitch are set with low covariance values. Conversely, states with higher uncertainty such as yaw, are initialized with higher covariance values.

References for the barometer and the GNSS module are set during the initialization as well. The initial altitude derived from the averaged barometric pressure measurement is defined as the reference altitude, and the initial GNSS position defines the origin of the world (NED) frame. All GNSS geodetic coordinates (WGS84) are converted to the world (NED) frame relative to this origin.

3) *Applying Sensor Calibration*: In this system, a clear distinction is made between additive errors and other errors regarding sensor calibration. Additive errors, such as hard iron distortions and offsets, are modeled as a part of the state biases. Therefore, no further manual compensation is required to compensate for these errors.

However, errors such as proportional errors and cross-axis errors cannot be estimated by the ESKF and must be manually compensated at every measurement cycle. The accelerometer scale factors obtained from six-point calibration, and sensor sensitivity values for the accelerometer and gyroscope, are applied to convert raw measurements into physically correct values.

For the magnetometer, soft iron distortion, which is a composition of a proportional error and a cross-axis error, must also be compensated for every measurement cycle. The soft iron matrix obtained from the ellipsoid fitting method is applied, ensuring that the ellipsoidal distortion is corrected.

4) *GNSS Accuracy Scaling & Clamping*: The accuracy indicators (hAcc, vAcc, and sAcc) provided by the GNSS module tend to be overly optimistic, often underestimating the actual measurement uncertainty. Direct usage of these values in the dynamic covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_{gnss} , results in a unrealistically small measurement noise covariance. This leads the filter to over-trust the GNSS measurements (i.e., yielding an excessively high Kalman gain), which enables it to be vulnerable to measurement noise, often resulting in a high frequency jitter.

To mitigate this, two methods are applied: minimum thresholding and scaling. A greatest lower bound is imposed on the accuracy values to prevent unrealistically small covariance during ideal reception conditions. Additionally, accuracy values are multiplied by a scale factor to correct the optimism provided, ensuring that the filter remains robust against temporary GNSS spikes or positional shifts.

5) *Gating & Data Integrity Check*: To ensure robust and reliable operation of the ESKF against outliers, each measurement undergoes a series of integrity checks and data gating before being used in the filter.

Timestamp & Numerical Validity: Basic sanity checks are applied to every incoming data. Measurements containing non-finite values such as NaN or infinity are ignored. In addition,

data indicating time reversal or excessively large time gaps are rejected.

Sensor Data Checks: Measurements that violate physical limitations are ignored. For instance, GNSS velocity measurements greater than 100m/s or magnetometer measurements with a magnitude greater than three times the normal Earth magnetic field magnitude are regarded as invalid. Furthermore, GNSS data are only accepted when the received 'Fix Type' indicates a valid data reception, ensuring that unreliable measurements are not used in the filter.

Innovation Gating: Even if the data are physically valid, temporary sensor glitches may still produce outliers. After the computation of the innovation $\mathbf{y} - h(\mathbf{x}_t)$, a gating is applied to ensure that the ESKF update is skipped when the innovation magnitude exceeds the pre-defined threshold.

These mechanisms prevent improbable measurements and data from destabilizing the filter.

6) *Covariance Symmetrization*: Although the Joseph form update introduced in Section IV-D theoretically guarantees the symmetry of the error covariance matrix \mathbf{P} , accumulated floating-point errors can produce small asymmetries after recursive update computations. Such asymmetry can eventually lead to filter divergence. To prevent this, symmetry is enforced after every covariance prediction and update computation using the following formulation.

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{P}^T)$$

This ensures that the \mathbf{P} maintain its symmetric form, which is a fundamental premise for the ESKF.

7) *Numerical Stability in Quaternion Operations*: Numerical stability in quaternion operations is essential during quaternion attitude prediction and recursive state updates.

When computing $\delta\mathbf{q}$, extremely small rotation magnitudes can lead to unstable computations (e.g., division by zero during the orientation computation using the exponential map). To prevent this, if the norm of the rotation falls below a pre-defined threshold ϵ , the rotation is treated as a negligible rotation and $\delta\mathbf{q}$ is set as an identity quaternion.

A fundamental premise of the ESKF is that the quaternion must maintain a unit quaternion form ($\|\mathbf{q}\| = 1$). If this prerequisite is violated, the corresponding rotation matrix loses its orthogonality, which creates distortions in the system. In practical implementations, accumulated floating-point errors cause the quaternion to drift away from the ideal unit form over time. To mitigate this, a renormalization is executed at the end of every quaternion prediction and update step.

$$\mathbf{q} = \frac{\mathbf{q}}{\|\mathbf{q}\|}$$

This ensures that the quaternion remains on the \mathbb{S}^3 manifold and always indicate a valid rotation.

V. CONTROLS

A. Control Architecture Overview

This section details the overall control architecture of the quadrotor UAV. As illustrated in Fig. 10, the control system

Fig. 10. **Block diagram of the cascaded control architecture.** The control system is designed as a two-layer cascaded architecture consisting of the outer loop (100Hz) for motion control and the inner loop (1kHz) for stabilization and tracking.

employs a cascaded architecture, separated into two distinct parts: a low-frequency outer control loop governing the motion behavior and a high-frequency inner control loop that stabilizes the vehicle and tracks the desired attitudes and angular rate.

The outer loop control runs at 100Hz based on user commands (e.g., velocity setpoints) and the estimated position $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$, velocity $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$, and quaternion attitude $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ from the ESKF. Based on positional and velocity errors, the control blocks compute the necessary acceleration and the reference yaw attitude, which is then converted into the desired quaternion attitude \mathbf{q}_d and the base thrust T . This layer translates the user commands into reference commands that must be tracked within the inner loop.

The inner loop control operates at 1kHz, to ensure robust vehicle stabilization and rapid attitude tracking. This layer receives the desired quaternion attitude \mathbf{q}_d , the desired yaw rate $\omega_{d,yaw}$, and the base thrust T from the outer loop. A quaternion PD control tracks the desired values to yield control moments (torque) \mathbf{M} . Finally, the motor mixer combines the base thrust T and the moments \mathbf{M} to calculate the individual motor throttle commands, transmitting the outputs to the ESC via DShot600 protocol.

B. Outer Loop Control Logic

The outer loop control is responsible for generating the reference commands from user commands. This section details on the control logic that is divided into three components: horizontal outer control, vertical outer control, and yaw command generation.

An interpretation of the user command input is described first, as it plays a crucial role in understanding the overall control logic. This system implements a mixed-frame velocity control interface, where commands are expressed in different frames.

In this Section V-B, vectors explicitly marked with the superscript B are expressed in the body frame. All others follow their natural reference frames unless stated otherwise.

- **Horizontal Control:** Joystick deflections correspond to the vehicle's desired horizontal velocity expressed in the body frame, denoted as ${}^B\text{stick}_{xy}$ later scaled into ${}^B\mathbf{v}_{d,xy}$.
- **Vertical Control:** Vertical joystick deflections command the vehicle's vertical velocity expressed in the world frame, denoted as stick_z later scaled into $\mathbf{v}_{d,z}$. This allows for independent altitude control regardless of the vehicle's attitude.
- **Yaw Control:** The yaw stick deflection serves as a yaw rate command, denoted in ${}^B\text{stick}_{yaw}$ later scaled into ${}^B\omega_{d,yaw}$, directly controlling the rate of heading change.

1) *Horizontal Control:* The horizontal controller computes the desired horizontal acceleration $\mathbf{a}_{d,xy}$ in the world frame. To achieve active maneuverability and stable hovering, the control logic switches between two different modes based on the user command input: horizontal velocity control mode and horizontal position hold mode.

Horizontal Velocity Control Mode: When an active joystick input is detected, the controller operates in a velocity control mode, allowing direct horizontal maneuvering based on the user input. Stick deflection, which is interpreted as the desired velocity in the body frame (${}^B\mathbf{v}_{d,xy}$), is first transformed into the world frame.

If this transformation is directly applied using the full rotation matrix derived from $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$, the vehicle's roll and pitch attitude would be coupled with the velocity vector leading to an unintended vertical motion during inclined maneuvers. To decouple horizontal movement from roll and pitch attitude, only the yaw component of the attitude is applied for the velocity transformation.

The body frame's X-axis vector is projected onto the world xy-plane and normalized to form a heading vector \mathbf{x}_{yaw} .

$$\mathbf{v}_x = \mathbf{R}\{\hat{\mathbf{q}}\}\mathbf{e}_x$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{proj} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_x$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{yaw} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{proj}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{proj}\|}$$

The rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_{yaw} is constructed and used for the transformation as follows.

$$\mathbf{R}_{yaw} = [\mathbf{x}_{yaw} \quad \mathbf{e}_z \times \mathbf{x}_{yaw} \quad \mathbf{e}_z]$$

$${}^W\mathbf{v}_{d,xy} = \mathbf{R}_{yaw} {}^B\mathbf{v}_{d,xy}$$

The error is then computed as the difference between the desired and estimated current velocities.

$$\mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} = \mathbf{v}_{d,xy} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{xy}$$

A Proportional-Integral (PI) control is applied to compute the desired acceleration.

$$\mathbf{a}_{d,xy} = K_{p,xy}^{vel} \mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} + K_{i,xy}^{vel} \int \mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} dt$$

Horizontal Position Hold Mode: When the joystick input returns to neutral (e.g., joystick is centered), the controller operates in a position hold mode. The horizontal position at that instant is fixed as the reference position $\mathbf{p}_{xy,ref}$. The error and acceleration computations are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_{pos,xy} &= \mathbf{p}_{xy,ref} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{xy}, \\ \mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} &= -\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{xy}, \\ \mathbf{a}_{d,xy} &= K_{p,xy}^{pos} \mathbf{e}_{pos,xy} + K_{p,xy}^{vel} \mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} + K_{i,xy}^{vel} \int \mathbf{e}_{vel,xy} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Here, the velocity error term is denoted as $-\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{xy}$ because the desired velocity is zero in position hold mode. Additionally, the velocity proportional term acts as a damping factor preventing overshoot.

2) *Vertical Control:* The vertical controller computes the desired vertical acceleration $a_{d,z}$, expressed in the world frame. Similar to the horizontal control, the vertical control logic switches between two modes based on the user command input: vertical velocity control mode and vertical position hold mode. Unlike the horizontal control, however, the vertical velocity is controlled directly in the world frame, reducing any additional computation for attitude dependent transformations, while also providing an intuitive control environment for the user.

Vertical Velocity Control Mode: When a joystick deflection is detected, the controller operates in a velocity control mode. The stick deflection is interpreted as the desired vertical velocity in the world frame ($\mathbf{v}_{d,z}$).

Note that the world frame utilizes the NED frame convention, where the positive Z-axis points downward. This requires a sign inversion to the user joystick input, before being applied to the controller.

The velocity error is computed as

$$e_{vel,z} = v_{d,z} - \hat{v}_z,$$

and a Proportional-Integral (PI) control is applied to compute the desired vertical acceleration.

$$a_{d,z} = K_{p,z}^{vel} e_{vel,z} + K_{i,z}^{vel} \int e_{vel,z} dt$$

Vertical Position Hold Mode: When the vertical joystick returns to the neutral state, the controller switches to the vertical position hold mode. Similar to the horizontal control logic, the estimated vertical position at the instant of mode transition is fixed as the reference vertical position $p_{z,ref}$. The control computation is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{pos,z} &= p_{z,ref} - \hat{p}_z \\ e_{vel,z} &= -\hat{v}_z \\ a_{d,z} &= K_{p,z}^{pos} e_{pos,z} + K_{p,z}^{vel} e_{vel,z} + K_{i,z}^{vel} \int e_{vel,z} dt \end{aligned}$$

3) *Yaw Command Generation:* Unlike the horizontal and vertical controller, the yaw logic is implemented as a command generation that converts the user command input into a desired yaw rate $\omega_{d,yaw}$ and a yaw attitude reference ψ_{ref} . The yaw command logic operates in two different modes depending on

the yaw joystick input: yaw rate control mode and yaw attitude hold mode.

Yaw Rate Control Mode: When the yaw joystick deflection is detected, the yaw rate mode begins to operate, enabling yaw rate control via user command. While this mode operates, yaw_{ref} is updated as the yaw attitude extracted from the estimated current quaternion attitude $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$. This ensures a smooth transition when entering the yaw attitude hold mode.

$$\psi_{ref} = \hat{\psi}$$

Yaw Attitude Hold Mode: When the yaw joystick returns to its neutral state, the yaw attitude hold mode is operated by the control logic. In this mode, the desired yaw rate $\omega_{d,yaw}$ is set to zero, and the update of the ψ_{ref} is suspended.

C. Desired Attitude & Thrust Generation

This section details the process of converting the computed accelerations and ψ_{ref} into the desired quaternion attitude \mathbf{q}_d and the base thrust T , which are used as inputs for the inner control loop.

1) *Desired Quaternion Generation:* The desired quaternion attitude \mathbf{q}_d is computed from the desired accelerations and the yaw attitude reference obtained earlier, from the outer loop control.

The desired body Z-axis direction, expressed in the world frame and denoted as $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$, is first determined from the desired acceleration values. Together with the yaw reference ψ_{ref} , the desired vehicle attitude is defined in the form of a rotation matrix. Given the desired acceleration \mathbf{a}_d in the world frame, the desired body Z-axis direction is defined as

$$\mathbf{z}_{d,body} = \mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_d = \begin{bmatrix} -a_{d,x} \\ -a_{d,y} \\ g - a_{d,z} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Fig. 11. Geometric construction of the desired body Z-axis direction $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$ obtained from acceleration \mathbf{a}_d and gravity \mathbf{g} in the world (NED) frame.

As illustrated in Fig. 11, the $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$ is aligned with the Z-axis of the body (FRD) frame. Since the rotation matrix must be orthogonal, $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$ must be normalized to be a unit vector.

$$\mathbf{z}_{d,body} = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{d,body}}{\|\mathbf{z}_{d,body}\|}$$

Next, the computed yaw reference ψ_{ref} is utilized to define a horizontal heading vector

$$\mathbf{x}_{heading} = [\cos \psi_{ref} \quad \sin \psi_{ref} \quad 0]^\top,$$

which represents the forward heading direction projected onto the horizontal plane. Using $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{heading}$, the remaining body axes expressed in the world frame can be calculated. Note that $\mathbf{z}_{d,body}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{heading}$ are generally not orthogonal, the calculated $\mathbf{y}_{d,body}$ must be re-normalized before calculating $\mathbf{x}_{d,body}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_{d,body} &= \mathbf{z}_{d,body} \times \mathbf{x}_{heading} \\ \mathbf{x}_{d,body} &= \mathbf{y}_{d,body} \times \mathbf{z}_{d,body} \end{aligned}$$

The desired rotation matrix is constructed by stacking the orthogonal body axes as columns.

$$\mathbf{R}_d = [\mathbf{x}_{d,body} \quad \mathbf{y}_{d,body} \quad \mathbf{z}_{d,body}]$$

The desired quaternion attitude \mathbf{q}_d is then obtained by converting \mathbf{R}_d into a quaternion form.

2) *Gravity & Attitude Thrust Loss Compensation:* The base thrust magnitude T is calculated to compensate for both gravitational force and thrust loss due to attitude tilt.

Although gravity could be compensated purely by the controller, this would require the controller to continuously operate around a large steady state command, related to the hover thrust. This approach increases the dynamic range of the control signal, which degrades numerical stability. Instead, gravity compensation is handled as a feedforward term, allowing the controller to focus on small errors.

When the vehicle is tilted to generate horizontal acceleration, the thrust vector is no longer aligned with the gravity vector. As a result, only the vertical component contributes to counteract gravity, while the remaining components are used for the horizontal motion. If not compensated, this produces a reduction in the vertical thrust component, resulting in an unintended altitude loss during horizontal maneuvers.

Note that the force vector \mathbf{f} is defined as the force applied to the air by the rotors, expressed in the world frame.

Using the similar logic from the desired quaternion generation, the required force vector expressed in the world, can be computed as

$$\mathbf{f} = m(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_d),$$

where m is the quadrotor UAV's mass.

Alternatively, the force vector can be computed as

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{R}\{\hat{\mathbf{q}}\} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ T \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{R}\{\hat{\mathbf{q}}\} T \mathbf{e}_z.$$

Here, $\mathbf{e}_z = [0 \quad 0 \quad 1]^\top$. Putting these formulations together, the base thrust magnitude T is computed as

$$T = \frac{m(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_d)_z}{(\mathbf{R}\{\hat{\mathbf{q}}\} \mathbf{e}_z)_z},$$

where $(\cdot)_z$ denotes the z component of the inner vector.

D. Inner Loop Control Logic

The inner loop control is responsible for the attitude stabilization and tracking of the desired attitude. Operating at 1kHz, this control loop ensures robust disturbance rejection and rapid tracking of the desired attitude. A quaternion Proportional-Derivative (PD) control is utilized to generate control moments \mathbf{M} , which are later converted into individual motor commands via the motor mixer.

The attitude error is computed directly using quaternions to avoid singularities inherent within the Euler angle representations. The quaternion error is defined as

$$\mathbf{q}_{error} = \hat{\mathbf{q}}^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{q}_d,$$

which is then split into a scalar part e_s and a vector part \mathbf{e}_v .

$$\mathbf{q}_{error} = \begin{bmatrix} e_s \\ \mathbf{e}_v \end{bmatrix}$$

To ensure that the vehicle rotates using the shortest path available, the vector error term is defined as

$$\mathbf{e}_q = 2\text{sign}(e_s)\mathbf{e}_v.$$

Using the fact that \mathbf{q} and $-\mathbf{q}$ represent the same physical orientation while implying different rotation paths, the $\text{sign}(e_s)$ ensures that the error term \mathbf{e}_q rotates the vehicle along the shortest path.

The angular rate error is computed as

$$\mathbf{e}_\omega = \boldsymbol{\omega}_d - \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}.$$

Here, the desired angular rate $\boldsymbol{\omega}_d$ is defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_d = [0 \quad 0 \quad \omega_{d,yaw}]^\top,$$

where the desired roll and pitch rate are set to zero for stabilization. Using these two errors, Proportional-Derivative (PD) control is applied as

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{K}_p^q \mathbf{e}_q + \mathbf{K}_d^\omega \mathbf{e}_\omega,$$

where \mathbf{K}_p^q and \mathbf{K}_d^ω are diagonal gain matrices, applying appropriate gains for each axes.

The computed control moments are normalized by the maximum available torque of the vehicle, before being passed down to the motor mixer. These limits are derived from the quadrotor UAV structure and the torque limits of the actuation system.

Fig. 12. Quadrotor motor rotation directions and body frame convention.

E. Motor Mixing

The motor mixer converts the computed base thrust $T \in [0, 1]$ and moment $\mathbf{M} = [M_R \ M_P \ M_Y]$, where each moment represents a normalized value $\in [-1, 1]$, into individual motor throttle commands. The motor arrangement of the system is illustrated in Fig. 12, which utilizes an X-configuration. In this arrangement, motor 2 and 3 rotate clockwise (CW), while motor 1 and 4 rotate counter clockwise (CCW).

Following the right-hand rule convention for roll, pitch, and yaw moment, the individual motor commands are defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} C1 &= T - M_R + M_P + M_Y \\ C2 &= T + M_R + M_P - M_Y \\ C3 &= T - M_R - M_P - M_Y \\ C4 &= T + M_R - M_P + M_Y \end{aligned}$$

These raw commands must be post-processed to ensure a valid input for the ESC. The mixer utilizes a dynamic saturation method to manage the commands. First, the command spread (difference between the maximum and minimum command) is calculated. If this spread exceeds the available range (i.e., > 1.0), the commands are normalized while preserving the command ratios. If the spread is within the limit, but shifted out of valid boundary (i.e., > 1.0 or < 0.0), the commands are linearly shifted to fit within $[0, 1]$. While this method inevitably produces distortion to the raw command distribution, it minimizes such distortion while ensuring actuator feasibility.

To prevent the motor from stopping during flight, a minimum idle thrust is enforced when the vehicle is armed and airborne. This ensures problems such as motor reactivation delay and the loss of thrust continuity, to not happen during flight.

The resulting commands are then transmitted to the ESC using the DShot600 protocol, which is detailed in Section III-B.

F. Control Implementation Details

To ensure robust performance and stability, several implementation details are applied within the system.

Joystick Input Deadband: Raw control signals from the RF receiver are susceptible to noise. Even when the joystick is centered, small fluctuations can occur, potentially causing vehicle jitter or drift.

To mitigate this, a deadband threshold is applied to the raw inputs. Any input value within this threshold is treated as zero, corresponding to a neutral command. This ensures that the controller ignores minor noises around the joystick center position, preventing unintended control commands during hovering.

Maximum Angle Limitation: Although quaternions provide a singularity free attitude representation, a constraint on the maximum tilt angle is enforced to the system. Since the quadrotor UAV relies on the vertical thrust component to counteract gravity, excessive tilting reduces the vertical thrust and can lead to crashes. This constraint ensures that sufficient vertical thrust is maintained, preventing irrecoverable thrust loss during maneuvers.

Integrator Anti-Windup: The integral terms in the outer control loop are effective for eliminating steady-state errors. However, when actuators become saturated while the error continues to accumulate, this can lead to an integrator windup, losing control of the system.

To prevent this, a clamping mechanism is applied to limit the magnitude of the accumulated integral term. Furthermore, while the vehicle is on the ground, the integrators are set to zero ensuring takeoffs to begin with a clean state.

D-term Low-Pass Filtering: The derivative term in the quaternion PD controller is highly sensitive to sensor noise. To mitigate this, raw angular velocity measurements from the IMU are first processed through a low-pass filter (LPF). The estimated gyroscope bias provided by the ESKF is then subtracted from the filtered value. This resulting clean estimate is used to compute the rate error required for the quaternion PD control.

Heading Singularity Handling: When executing computations in the control system, the vehicle's heading is determined by projecting the X-axis of the body frame onto the horizontal plane of the world frame. However, as the pitch angle approaches 90° , this projection on the horizontal plane vanishes, leaving the heading undefined.

To prevent this geometric singularity, the norm of the projected vector is continuously monitored. If the norm falls below a predefined threshold ϵ , the heading update is skipped and the last valid heading is retained for computation. This ensures numerical stability and stable yaw control even in extreme maneuvers.

Arming and In Air Mode: To ensure operational safety, a two-stage activation logic is implemented.

Upon entering the 'Armed state' the motors spin at a fixed idle speed to indicate motor activation, while control inputs remain disabled. This state allows verification of the motor readiness without any control inputs.

The 'In Air Mode' is engaged when the actual flight is initiated. In this mode, the user command inputs and controllers are fully activated, enabling the vehicle to be fully operational.

This two-stage activation logic prevents unintended maneuvers immediately after motor activation, and improves system safety while the vehicle is on the ground.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents experimental results obtained from the proposed flight control system to demonstrate the practical feasibility and stability of the implemented architecture.

A. Real-time Performance Analysis

To verify the deterministic behavior of the FC, the loop period and computational load of the Integrated Control Task were analyzed. To minimize additional CPU overhead introduced by the logging method during the experiment, a DMA-based logging method was employed for time measurements.

Fig. 13 illustrates the distribution of the main control loop period measured over 13,209 samples.

Fig. 13. **Histogram of the measured main control loop period.** The dashed line indicates the mean value of the measurements.

The statistical results reveal a mean period of $997.07\mu s$. Although a small systematic offset of approximately 0.3% from the 1ms target period is observed, the standard deviation (σ) was presented as $0.31\mu s$. The maximum loop period recorded is observed as $1000.4\mu s$ exceeding $0.4\mu s$ beyond the 1ms target. This confirms the stable timing behavior of the main control loop.

Next, Fig. 14 presents the execution time to evaluate the computational load driven by the main control loop.

Fig. 14. **Execution time of the main control loop over time.** The red dashed line represents the 1ms real-time deadline.

The average execution time is measured at $41.66\mu s$, resulting in a CPU load of approximately 4.2%. The worst case execution time measured was $56.1\mu s$, which is within the $1000\mu s$ deadline provided. This leaves a substantial timing margin for other tasks to function while preserving a deterministic execution.

These results demonstrate that the system guarantees a deterministic real-time operation with low-computational load in the highest-frequency loop.

B. Barometer Shielding and Noise Analysis

To ensure precise altitude estimation, the barometer must measure pressure while rejecting aerodynamic disturbances. Since the ESKF relies on low-frequency barometer measurements, pressure noise in the low-frequency band directly degrades the estimation performance. To mitigate this, an open-cell foam shield was installed, as is detailed in Section II-G.

To evaluate the shielding effectiveness, pressure data was measured in a stationary position under varying throttle conditions. Fig. 15 shows the comparison of the mean-centered pressure fluctuations at 50% throttle, using 250 samples ($\approx 12.5s$ at 20Hz).

Fig. 15. **Comparison of mean-centered pressure fluctuations.** The data was collected at 50% throttle while in a stationary position.

The shielded sensor yielded a standard deviation of 0.065mbar , while the unshielded sensor's standard deviation was 0.095mbar . The quantitative analysis demonstrates a 31.4% reduction in standard deviation and a 32.9% reduction in the peak-to-peak amplitude within the central 95% measurements.

For further analysis of the noise frequency, Fig. 16 illustrates the noise spectral density obtained by a Power Spectral Density(PSD) analysis using the Welch method.

The Welch PSD analysis reveals a general noise reduction across the spectrum. Low-frequency noise power, which is critical for the vertical movement of the vehicle, is reduced by 57.7% in the 0-10Hz band and by 76.9% in the 0-2Hz band. This prevents the ESKF from misinterpreting aerodynamic disturbances as actual altitude changes.

Fig. 16. Welch power spectral density (PSD) analysis of the mean-centered pressure fluctuations.

Although the shield generally reduces noise, a persistent peak around 5Hz is observed in both conditions. As this component is largely unaffected by the shielding, it is likely that the noise is attributed to mechanical vibrations or the resonance of the vibration damper.

Furthermore, a correlation was found between the effectiveness of the shielding and the disturbance intensity. At lower throttle settings (30% and 40%), the reduction in standard deviation was less (3.8% and 21.4%) compared to the higher throttle setting (31.4% reduction at 50% throttle setting). This correlation indicates that the shielding becomes more critical during more aggressive maneuvers.

C. Magnetometer Calibration

Accurate heading estimation is crucial for precise yaw estimation and stability in the quadrotor UAV. However, since magnetometers are susceptible to magnetic distortions, calibration is an essential process. The ellipsoid fitting method is used to compensate for both the hard iron and soft iron distortions in the magnetometer measurements.

Fig. 17 presents the comparison between raw and calibrated magnetometer measurements collected by rotating the the quadrotor UAV.

As illustrated, the raw measurements contain an offset, shifting the center of the data away from the origin (hard iron distortion). Furthermore, the data distribution forms an ellipsoid rather than a perfect sphere (soft iron distortion).

Through the ellipsoid fitting process, the hard iron bias vector \mathbf{h} and soft iron transformation matrix \mathbf{s} are computed as follows.

$$\mathbf{h} = \begin{bmatrix} -23.1509 \\ 0.0430942 \\ 9.95012 \end{bmatrix} \mu\text{T}$$

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.29515 & 0.00545819 & -0.0387866 \\ 0.00545819 & 1.35978 & -0.0179428 \\ -0.0387866 & -0.0179428 & 1.45085 \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 17. Magnetometer calibration results using ellipsoid fitting. (a) Raw magnetometer measurements and (b) calibrated measurements are shown as 3-plane scatter plots (XY, XZ, and YZ projections).

After applying the calibration parameters, the measurements are transformed as shown in Fig. 17. The calibrated measurements form a sphere centered at $(0, 0, 0)\mu\text{T}$ with a radius corresponding to the local magnetic field strength. This calibration ensures robust yaw estimation for the ESKF.

D. Attitude Estimation Validation

This section validates the performance of the ESKF attitude estimation through a series of experiments. Due to the absence of a high-precision ground truth system, quantitative error analysis was not conducted. Therefore, the validation focuses on verifying the dynamic consistency, axis-decoupling, and noise rejection performance of the ESKF under roll, pitch, and yaw maneuvers.

All experiments were conducted through manually manipulated motion. Although internal computations utilize quaternions, the results are converted to Euler angles for intuitive visualization. The attitude estimates were logged at 200Hz for visualization and analysis.

Roll Maneuver: As illustrated in Fig. 18(a), a roll tilt-hold-return experiment was performed, presenting estimated attitude angles from the ESKF. The 'Roll (Acc)' represents the raw roll angle calculated solely from accelerometer measurements, without using the filter.

The estimated roll angle presents a smooth response while tilting the vehicle, effectively filtering out the noises observed in the accelerometer measurements. During the hold phase, the estimation remains stable with minimal drift.

Furthermore, the pitch angle maintains a value near zero, and the yaw angle shows minor fluctuations. These fluctuations in the yaw angle are likely attributed to unintentional coupling during manual manipulation in the experiment, rather than filter instability. These results indicate that the ESKF achieves stable estimation and axis-decoupling.

To validate the response of the filter to dynamic movement, a continuous sinusoidal maneuver was performed as shown in Fig. 18(b). As illustrated, the ESKF tracks the motion smoothly without instability. Both pitch and yaw angles remaining stable near the initial values, and not drifting, indicate an isolation of the axes. The minor angle fluctuations that

(a) Roll tilt-hold-return.

(b) Roll axis sinusoidal motion.

Fig. 18. **Attitude estimation during roll maneuvers over time.** (a) demonstrates attitude estimation while conducting a roll tilt-hold-return maneuver. The 'Roll (Acc)' represents the accelerometer-based roll angle. (b) illustrates the tracking capability and axis-decoupling during a continuous sinusoidal motion around the roll axis.

(a) Pitch tilt-hold-return.

(b) Pitch axis sinusoidal motion.

Fig. 19. **Attitude estimation during pitch maneuvers over time.** (a) demonstrates attitude estimation while conducting a pitch tilt-hold-return maneuver. The 'Pitch (Acc)' represents the accelerometer-based pitch angle. (b) illustrates the tracking capability and axis-decoupling during a continuous sinusoidal motion around the pitch axis.

are only observed during the maneuver are likely caused by unintentional coupling during manual manipulation, as mentioned earlier.

Pitch Maneuver: A similar experiment was conducted for the pitch axis. Fig. 19(a) shows the pitch tilt-hold-return maneuver, while Fig. 19(b) illustrates the estimated attitude during a continuous sinusoidal motion around the pitch axis. The observed results are consistent with the results obtained from the roll maneuver experiments.

Yaw Maneuver: To evaluate the stability and consistency of the ESKF heading estimation, a continuous yaw rotation experiment was conducted, as shown in Fig. 20. This experiment provides the estimated attitude during continuous yaw rotation.

The estimated yaw angle exhibits a wrap-around behavior at $\pm 180^\circ$, which is an inherent characteristic of the Euler angle representation during continuous rotation. The roll and pitch angles remained near zero while rotating. This confirms that the ESKF maintains axis decoupling and that the calibrated magnetometer provides robust measurements for stable yaw estimation without filter divergence.

E. Consistency Validation of Vertical State Estimation

To validate the physical consistency between the actual motion of the vehicle and the state estimated by the ESKF,

the vertical motion of the vehicle was analyzed. The vehicle was manually lifted, held stationary, and then translated down back to its initial height. All measurements were logged at 200Hz.

Fig. 21 illustrates the estimated vertical position and veloc-

Fig. 20. **Attitude estimation during continuous yaw rotation.** The yaw angle shows the Euler angle wrap-around behavior.

Fig. 21. **Estimated vertical position and velocity during vertical motion.** The vehicle is translated upward, held stationary, and then translated downward. Note that the NED frame is utilized.

ity over time. The NED frame is used, where the positive Z-axis points downward. During the upward motion, the estimated vertical velocity becomes negative and the vertical position value decreases accordingly. While the vehicle remains stationary ($11s < t < 15s$), the vertical velocity stays near zero, and the vertical position presents no noticeable drift. Then the downward motion induces a positive velocity returning to its original position, though some noise is observed.

No noticeable divergence or nonphysical behavior was observed within the motion, indicating that the estimated vertical states remain physically consistent with the actual vehicle movement.

F. Effect of Barometer Measurement Update on Vertical State Estimation

To analyze the contribution of barometer measurement updates to the stability of the ESKF estimation, the estimated vertical position and its corresponding variance were observed under stationary conditions, with the barometer update enabled and disabled. Although the barometer update affects the entire system, this experiment analyzes only the vertical position due to its direct correlation. The experiment was conducted under static conditions.

Fig. 22(a) represents the estimated vertical position over time. When the barometer update is disabled, a gradual drift is observed starting from approximately 20s. In contrast, when the barometer update is enabled, the vertical position remains near a constant value, indicating a functional correction of the accumulated errors by the ESKF.

Fig. 22(b) illustrates the time evolution of the vertical position variance, in which the initial value is set as $10^{-2}m^2$. Without barometer updates, the variance increases over time, reflecting increased uncertainty in the vertical position estimation. When the barometer update is enabled, the variance converges to a small value, indicating a reduction in the

(a) Estimated vertical position over time.

(b) Variance of the vertical position over time.

Fig. 22. **Comparison of the vertical state and variance estimation, with and without barometer measurement update in a stationary condition.** (a) represents the estimated vertical position and (b) shows the vertical position variance on a logarithmic scale. The vertical position variance is the diagonal element of the covariance matrix corresponding to the vertical position.

uncertainty of the vertical position estimation due to barometer corrections.

In particular, a jump in the estimated vertical position is observed immediately after enabling the barometer update. Although the magnitude of the jump varies slightly between experiments, this issue constantly appears in the same direction immediately after the filter activation, which is caused by an initial offset inherent in the raw altitude derived from barometer pressure measurements. Upon barometer update operation, the ESKF deterministically realigns the vertical position estimate with the barometer measurements. Since the estimate remains stable and bounded after this correction, the observed jump is interpreted as the filter's responsiveness to measurement updates, rather than as a filter instability. While this behavior does not degrade the overall estimation performance, it suggests that a more refined barometer initialization process could mitigate such initial altitude jumps.

These results validate the role of the barometer measurement update in the ESKF by providing corrections that maintain the stability of the estimation, prevent long-term drift, and bounds the uncertainty within the system.

State Estimation Under Static Condition: To observe the long-term stability and drift characteristics of the ESKF, a stationary condition experiment was conducted. The vehicle remained stationary for approximately 4 minutes while the estimated position and velocity were logged.

Fig. 23 presents the estimated position and velocity over time. As shown, the velocity estimates rapidly converge and

Fig. 23. Estimated position and velocity under static conditions. The estimations are logged while the vehicle remains stationary for 4 minutes.

remain bounded near zero. Minor fluctuations correspond to sensor noise, which is suppressed without causing filter divergence.

The position estimates, on the other hand, present a slow wandering behavior over time, especially prominent in the horizontal axes. This is primarily attributed to the inherent wandering behavior in the GNSS measurements. As the ESKF utilizes a GNSS measurement update, the filter reflects this wandering behavior by estimating small apparent motions, even though the vehicle stays stationary. This result indicates that the filter does not explicitly filter out the GNSS wandering under static conditions.

The vertical position jump is observed at the beginning, which has been explained in the vertical state estimation experiment. Overall, the ESKF maintains stable velocity estimates, while showing bounded position wandering under static conditions. These results present both robustness and limitations of the current filter algorithm.

State Estimation During Hovering Flight: To validate the performance of the ESKF under actual flight conditions, a real-flight hovering experiment was conducted. After lift-off, the vehicle maintained a hovering state for a short period of time and then landed on the ground.

As illustrated in Fig. 24, the estimated position, velocity, and attitude are shown over time. An initial jump in the vertical position estimation is observed, the cause of which has been mentioned previously. The vehicle lifts off the ground at approximately 8s, resulting in a negative vertical velocity with the corresponding position transition. After hovering in the air, the vehicle lands on the ground approximately at 35s, which reflects a positive vertical velocity and a positive vertical position transition.

The position estimates remain bounded without filter di-

Fig. 24. Estimated position, velocity, and attitude during hovering flight. The vehicle goes through a lift-off, hover, and landing action.

vergence during the flight. Although minor variations are observed, the overall behavior of the filter remains consistent with the actual physical motion of the vehicle.

The estimated velocity remains near zero during the hovering phase, indicating a stable hovering condition. The attitude estimates also stay stable throughout the process. Fluctuations observed during the landing phase are likely caused by the physical impact between the vehicle and the ground.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the ESKF provides a physically consistent and stable state estimation without filter divergence, validating its applicability to practical flight conditions.

VII. CONCLUSION

This document presented the design, implementation, and experimental validation of a custom quadrotor UAV flight controller. By integrating a real-time firmware architecture and an Error-State Kalman Filter with a quaternion-based cascaded control architecture, the proposed system achieved robust and stable flight performance on resource-constrained embedded hardware.

Experimental results demonstrated stable and physically consistent state estimation under various operating conditions. These results confirm that advanced state estimation and control algorithms can be reliably executed within strict real-time constraints.

Finally, the analysis identifies specific limitations, such as sensor initialization and estimation drift induced by GNSS wandering effects, which indicate directions for further refinement. Overall, this document provides a comprehensive foundation for the development of custom flight control systems and serves as a basis for future research.

REFERENCES

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